

ECONOMIC EDUCATION FOR YOUNG CHILDREN

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Abstract. The article provides information on the implementation of economic education in pre-school educational institutions, the purpose of providing economic education, introducing children of pre-school age to the first economic concepts and terms.

Аннотация. В статье представлена информация о реализации экономического образования в дошкольных образовательных учреждениях, целях обеспечения экономического образования, ознакомления детей дошкольного возраста с первыми экономическими понятиями и терминами.

Keywords. Education, economic education, income, expenses, work, thrift, society, market, entrepreneurship.

Ключевые слова. Образование, экономическое образование, доходы, расходы, труд, бережливость, общество, рынок, предпринимательство.

After Uzbekistan gained its independence, raising the economic culture became one of the important tasks of the state. Major changes were made to the socially oriented market economy, and a serious foundation was created for the formation of market culture. The basis of freedom of economic management, which is one of the main factors of the development of economic culture, has been provided. Market of the country's economy in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan it was determined that all forms of property have equal rights and that they are protected in every way, that private property is also under state protection. A wide path has been opened for economic activity, entrepreneurship and freedom of work. The main attention is paid to expanding the level of economic knowledge and skills of the population, the ability to think economically, to strengthen the creative approach to work, to activate their participation in entrepreneurial activities, and favorable conditions are being created for their implementation. The purpose of economic education carried out in pre-school educational institutions is to prepare children to acquire economic knowledge, skills and abilities. In order to achieve this goal, it is necessary to successfully solve the following tasks:

- 1) development of various situations that allow expanding and deepening the scope of thinking of children of preschool age;
- 2) creation of necessary pedagogical conditions for solving situations related to economic concepts;
- 3) development and implementation of a set of games that provide a basis for acquiring economic knowledge and develop logical-mathematical imagination.

Implementation of economic education in pre-school educational institutions starts from the middle group, and according to the "Early economic education-education program", it is envisaged to introduce children to six different economic

concepts in this age group: 1) economy; 2) labor; 3) wealth; 4) property relations; 5) market; 6) money.

For the children of the older age group, knowledge about the following eight types of economic concepts will be included, along with a broader and more complete coverage of the concepts intended to be taught in the middle group: 1) economy; 2) labor; 3) wealth; 4) property relations; 5) entrepreneurship; 6) market; 7) money; 8) product.

In the preparatory group for school, the contents of eleven different economic concepts are explained: 1) economy; 2) labor; 3) family; 4) society; 5) communication; 6) spirituality; 7) maintenance of rules and order; 8) management; 9) trade; 10) money; 11) product.

The content of primary economic education and upbringing of preschool educational institutions is "Acquiring knowledge about the environment and understanding it" and . It is carried out on the basis of training on the formation of "elementary mathematical knowledge and skills". Our children involuntarily encounter economics from an early age. They are armed with concepts such as "mine", "ours", "rich", "cheap", "expensive", "buy", "sell", "money" in the family from the first age. Therefore, we should continue what children learn in the family in kindergarten, that is, we should teach them the first simple economic concepts.

Economic education teaches the young generation to think about the development of economic knowledge and skills, thrift, diligence, initiative, and economic activity. What is the economy, the economy itself? This concept was introduced by the Greek scientist Heliot, which means "household management industry". Later, the essence of this concept was expanded and its meaning was filled. Economy is a very broad and complex concept. So, the economy is the main aspect of

human activity, it is the most important basis of society, its foundation. The purpose of economic education should be to prepare a person for economic activity, to participate in the economic life of our society, to form diligent and active citizens of the republic. Economic laws of development of society in the minds of children. Introducing children of preschool age to the first economic concepts and terms can be the basis for their growth and development as a person. Therefore, every group educator should know the requirements of the program for introducing children to the first economic lessons, i.e., the scope of concepts given to children and the ways and methods of their implementation.

List of used literature:

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